

The Role of Globalization in Advancing Women's Rights

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Abstract

Globalization has emerged as a powerful force shaping social, economic, and political structures across the world, significantly influencing the advancement of women's rights. Through increased cross-border interactions, the spread of information and communication technologies, and the expansion of global markets, globalization has facilitated greater awareness of gender equality and human rights. Globalization is empowering the women across the globe. It is helping for the women to involving in different situation like as political, social, economic, sports and cultural. Women empowerment stands for expansion of assets and capabilities of women to participate in different area, control and hold accountable institutions that affect their lives. Globalization needs to manage the situation well and look globally instead of thinking just locally. Policies framed by the different countries helping the women to know about their rights and enhancing their skills at the competitive edge.

Keywords: Globalization, Women Right, Education, Empower.

1. Introduction:

Globalization is paving a way for the women to know about their rights and to make them empower so that they can become self-dependant, the Indian state in view of its commitment to various international conventions specially "Mexico plan of action (1975)" the Nairobi forward looking strategies (1985) the Beijing declaration as well as the platform for action (1995) and the outcome document adopted by the UNGA session on gender equality and development and peace for the 21st century, titled further

actions and institutions to implement the Beijing declaration and the platform for action have been unreservedly endorsed by India for appropriate follow-up key among them is the ratification of the "convention on elimination of all forms of discrimination against women (CEDAW)" in 1993. Government of India, other countries and many international organizations have drafted many good policies to aware the women about their rights. In the past we have witnessed that women were au fait about their rights, now a days we can see that due to globalization women are working in different fields of the world whether its sports, corporate, film industry and many others.

Government of India has framed a policy called national policy for the empowerment of women (2001) this policy is bringing an awareness among the women, most of the women do not know that constitution not only grant equality to women, but also empowers the state to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favor of women, within the framework of a democratic polity, our laws, development policies, plans and programmes have aimed at women's advancement in different spheres.

From the fifth five year plan (1974-78) onwards has been a marked shift in the approach to women's issues from welfare to development.

The national commission for women was set up by an act of parliament in 1990 to safeguards the rights and legal entitlements of women, the 73rd and 74th amendments (1993) to the constitution of India have provided for reservation of seats in the local bodies of panchayats and municipalities for women, laying a strong foundation for their

participation in decision making at the local levels.

India has also ratified various international conventions and human rights instruments committing to secure equal rights of women, key among them is the ratification of the convention on elimination of all forms of discrimination against women (CEDAW) in 1993.

1. Globalization: Globalization refers to the increasing integration and interdependence of countries and people across the world through trade, investment, technology, communication, and cultural exchange. It reduces geographical barriers and connects local societies to the global system as well as means to know about the social, political and economic empowerment of the women through their status. Globalization is a mode of sharing of the experiences, exchange of ideas, technology and network of the institutions and organizations through bilateral and multilateral arrangements. There are various means by which globalization mitigate the cross border problems with the help of air planes, telephone services, e-mails and instant capital flows (global policies forum (2011)). as globalization strengthening partnerships with civil society, particularly women organizations. It is the “phenomenon of increased integration of the world economy as evidenced by the international trade and factor mobility”. Globalization with the help of positive economic and social policies helping women to empower themselves so that they can realize their full potential as well as globalization is building and strengthening partnerships with civil society, particularly women’s organizations.

2 Perspectives of globalization: It is quite lucid that there are two main linchpins of globalization as per words of Irani and Noruzi, 2011 and they are as follows:

(a). Pro-globalization

(b). Anti-globalization

(a). Pro-globalization:

As for as globalization is concern it produce more efficient competitive edge for women

and having more pros as compare to cons which help women to show their influence around the globe in more effective ways.

(b). Anti-globalization:

Countries supporting the anti globalization have less capable competitive approach around the globe. Hence increased competitive competition among the women in the different spheres like political, cultural and many others and it might keep them deprived for showing their influence/talent around the globe.

3. Globalization effects on women empowerment:

Globalization is helping most of the countries to eliminate the discrimination and all forms of violence against women and the girl child, it is providing equal access to health care, quality education at all levels, employment, equal remuneration, occupational health and safety, social security and ensuring provisions of the women basic needs several program would be initiated globally:

- Ensure food security.
- Arrange for housing and shelter.
- Provide equal education.
- Devise a holistic approach to women health.
- Formulate macro economic and social policies institutionalizing women participation in economic development.
- Arrange support services like child care facility etc to enable the women to come to come at competitive edge to recognized themselves more effectively around the globe.

4. Important factors for making effective globalisation on women:

Empowerment: In last two decades technological development has created a tremendous impact on the lives of the women in the developing nations, as per the word globalization it contains a complex economic, political, cultural and geographic process in which the mobility of the capital, organizations ,ideas, discourses and people have taken global or trans-national

form (1999) all this is possible due to electronic development like intranet, mobiles, telephones, satellites, cellular phones (investor ord 2005), moreover with the establishment of international free trade policies such as north america free trade agreement (NAFTA) and others, trans-national corporational are using the profits motives to guide their factories toward developing nation in search of “cheap female labor”. corporation prefer female labor over male labor because women are considered to be “docile” workers, who are willing to obey production demand at any price, mostly in developing nations type of works such as garment industry is considered to be female domestic roles therefore cultural influence in developing nation also impact employment stratification.

5. Results and conclusions:

Our analysis of globalization and its impact on women reveals that political human rights are more monitored than economic and social human rights. however, factors that constitute human rights for many people and especially women are within the realms of social and economic structures. it is the role of the human rights regimes to monitor and enforce the “global village” to address economic, social and political rights effectively on equal basis with civil and political rights in order to capture the needs of all people and in particular women, the reorganization of human regimes should be a priority in the 21st century in enforcing multinational corporations take more responsibilities and accountabilities in social and economic structures that limit people in the third world and women in particular from access to resources at a global level, the power and the control of world resources through globalization should be monitored regularly by the national state and international human rights instruments.

Inspite of increasing encroachments on the state’s autonomy due to globalization, the state is still the main reference point of governance and continues to have certain responsibilities, especially in the area of policy making and implementation. it should demand

from corporations codes of conduct that include human rights law that would enforce and ensure the protection of marginalized people, since these corporations have no check and balances, its the national states responsibilities to formulate laws and regulations which should monitor and control corporations activities, these responsibilities should also ensure that corporation programs are consistent with people's customs, traditional farming systems and their overall well-being. this include women's ownership to land and other production resources, health care delivery, education, shelter, clean water, save working conditions, and transportation and sustainable environment among other resources, the state should ensure that in the areas of land tenure and education policies are needed that advance and empowerment women through an education system that include legal literacy, these factors will empower women in ways that better enable them to access necessities of life such as food security, shelter, credit, and to enhance their autonomy in decision making, any state in its endeavor to achieve its goals, it should form a coalition with private sectors- civil society, religion, business, and media. women's ngos and especially ywca have been effective in addressing the needs for women, separate education for girls not based on colonial and post colonial education in the third world, but based on empowering women as individuals on their own rights as advocated by ywca in America (marihno, 1986) should be implemented along with legal literacy in the education curriculum for girls. women are not just victims, but respond to policies that shape their daily lives and through organizing collectively effect socioeconomic and political changes. nyamus example about women acquiring property outside the usual paradigm of family land is an important one. however, there are challenges too, especially lack of information, organizational abilities, encroachment by politicians. legal literacy will have a positive impact in these challenges. family as an institution in society, like the national state, should also

take responsibilities and accountability for women's education. It is at the family level that values, attitudes and perceptions about life are formed., values and gender stereotypes passed on children and perpetuated at household level have the ramifications of future policy decision making at state level or internationally. while women, traditionally have primary role of nurturing and teaching children, men should also take this as a challenge in enforcing values, positive attitudes in education of the children. education should include among other things the knowledge of social relations, attitudes and responsibilities of both children and parents in education, socioeconomic and political issues affecting their lives, gender perceptions and development policies from top-down have to change to reflect the needs of people.

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